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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 6

Pages: 615-621

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2288

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13627152

Manuscript Accepted: 08-02-2024

The TPACK Model, Students' Academic Performance in English, and Challenges of Its Use as Assessed by Teachers

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Abstract

Employing a mixed-method (quantitative-qualitative) research design that involved random assignment and purposive selection, this study delved into the effect of the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Model on the Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 students and the challenges of its use as assessed by the teachers. The qualitative data collected from the interview were translated, coded, categorized, and given specific themes. Results from the experimentation divulged that the group exposed to the TPACK had more students who got passing grades. Hence, the TPACK model showed promising chances of improving students' academic performance. Four themes emerged concerning the challenges of the use of the TPACK Model as assessed by the teachers namely: Connectivity/Internet Issues and Unavailability of Facilities, Students' Limited Knowledge of the Technology and Unavailability of Devices, Teacher's Limited Knowledge of the Technology, and Teacher's Interest/Time and Age. Lastly, findings showed a significant difference in students' academic performance in English, particularly in the experimental group exposed to the TPACK. Hence, it was noted that the TPACK model can help teachers teach English and other learning areas to improve students' academic performance. To this effect, the TPACK model is recommended in teaching English and other learning areas to supplement and enhance teaching methodologies. In achieving technology's significant role in teaching and learning, support facilities and development programs for teachers' capacity building and upskilling that will improve technology integration were humbly suggested.

Keywords: *TPACK, academic performance, English language teaching, challenges*

Introduction

Technology is increasingly recognized as a critical tool for enhancing the learning experience in the contemporary educational landscape. It offers innovative ways to engage students and improve teaching practices, making it essential for teachers to possess the necessary skills and knowledge for effective technology integration in the classroom. The Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework provides a comprehensive model that guides teachers in blending technology with pedagogical strategies and content delivery. This integration fosters a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, enhancing creativity, motivation, and academic performance (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

In the context of local schools in Carmen, Bohol, technology integration into teaching faces significant challenges. Many schools in this area struggle with limited access to technological resources, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient professional development opportunities for teachers. These challenges are compounded by the rapid pace of technological advancement and the increasing demand for digital literacy, which can impede the effective implementation of technology-enhanced instruction and affect students' learning outcomes. Despite existing studies highlighting the benefits of the TPACK framework and the challenges associated with technology integration, there is a notable gap in research focusing specifically on how this model can be effectively implemented in the unique context of local schools in Carmen. This underscores the need for a detailed examination of the TPACK framework's impact within such settings.

The researcher, having extensive experience in teaching English subjects, has observed that technology-enhanced lessons often result in increased student engagement and improved academic performance. This observation aligns with findings that teachers adept in technology integration are better equipped to support student achievement (Ammade et al., n.d.; Azturk & Ozturk, 2019). Despite these benefits, challenges persist in technology integration, including inadequate infrastructure and limited access to resources (Boonsue, 2021; Tanucan et al., 2021). Such barriers can hinder the effective implementation of technology and impact students' learning experiences.

Teachers, driven by a deep-seated commitment to their students' success, continuously seek methods to maximize the productivity of their instructional time. They strive to ensure that every moment spent in the classroom is purposeful and beneficial, avoiding wasted opportunities. Applying the TPACK framework is instrumental in achieving this goal by offering a structured approach to incorporating technology into teaching practices, thereby enriching the educational experience.

The Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) model underscores teachers' need to integrate technology seamlessly into their instructional practices. This model is anchored in theories such as Anchored Instruction, Dual-Coding Theory, and Constructivism, highlighting the benefits of using technology to enhance learning. Anchored Instruction emphasizes the role of technology in facilitating problem-solving and discovery (Bransford, 1992), while Dual-Coding Theory suggests that integrating visual and auditory inputs can improve information retention (Paivio, n.d.). Constructivism advocates for a student-centered approach where learners actively engage with technology to construct their understanding (Dewey, 1859-1952).

Given the rapid advancements in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and the increasing demand for digital literacy, integrating technology in teaching English has become indispensable. The TPACK model offers a framework for teachers to effectively combine technological tools with pedagogical strategies and content knowledge, thus enhancing students' learning outcomes (Koehler & Mishra, 2008). Despite its potential, the integration process has challenges, including technological limitations and resistance from some educators (Boonsue, 2021; Faud et al., 2020). This study aims to evaluate the impact of the TPACK model on students' academic performance in English and identify the challenges teachers face in its implementation within the local context. By addressing these issues, the research seeks to propose strategies for optimizing the use of technology in the classroom, ultimately contributing to a more effective and productive educational environment.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the effect of the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Model on the Academic Performance in English of Grade 11 students at Francisco L. Adlaon High School, Carmen, Bohol for the school year 2021-2022, and the challenges of its use as assessed by the teachers. The findings of this study served as a basis for proposing a program to maximize the use of TPACK model in the teaching of English. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the academic performance in English of students in the control group before and after exposure to traditional teaching and students in the experimental group before and after exposure to the TPACK?
2. What are the challenges in the use of the TPACK as assessed by the teachers?
3. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance in English of students in the control and experimental groups?
4. What intervention/program can be proposed to improve the teaching and learning of English?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a mixed-method design. It involved 60 Grade 11 students: 30 were randomly assigned to a control group, and 30 were purposively selected for the experimental group, which received a TPACK model intervention. Both groups took pre-tests and post-tests to measure competency changes. Additionally, teachers were interviewed about challenges with the TPACK model. Combining experimental and interview methods improved validity and minimized bias.

Participants

The study involved 130 Grade 11 students from Francisco L. Adlaon High School. Thirty students were purposively selected for the experimental group (those enrolled in limited face-to-face classes), while 30 students for the control group were randomly assigned. This randomization ensured that all students had an equal chance of being assigned to either group.

A total of 60 students participated in the study, which was deemed sufficient for making generalizations. Inclusion criteria were: (1) Grade 11 students enrolled at Francisco L. Adlaon High School, (2) regular attendance in modular and limited face-to-face classes, (3) understanding of the study, and (4) parental consent. Exclusion criteria included unwillingness to participate, uncooperative behavior, and hesitancy in answering tests. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Additionally, five English teachers were purposively selected for interviews to provide qualitative insights on the challenges of using the model.

Instrument

A 40-item multiple-choice test was administered to measure the before and after students' academic performance in English. The test covered the fourth quarter learning competencies and lessons in Grade 11 senior high school core subject, Reading and Writing.

Also, an unstructured interview was conducted to a group of five teachers handling and teaching English subjects assessing and yielding data on the challenges on the use of the TPACK model. The second part involves a 21-item checklist distributed to educators to assess affective, continuance, and normative commitment levels. Checklist items are derived from Allen and Meyer's 1990 instrument dedicated to evaluating commitment factors.

Procedure

The data-gathering process began with obtaining permissions from the Superintendent of the Division of Bohol, the Public Schools District Supervisor, and the School Principal of Francisco L. Adlaon High School, including approval from the LGU and Rural Health Unit. Consent letters detailing the study's purpose, procedures, and participants' rights were sent to parents, ensuring voluntary participation and the right to withdraw without penalty. Data confidentiality was maintained, and cultural and health protocols were followed. A 40-item test based on the Department of Education's fourth-quarter competencies was developed, reviewed, and pilot-tested with 20 students for reliability. The experimental group received lessons integrated with the TPACK model, while the control group used only printed modules. After completing the competencies, both groups took a final test, which research assistants scored for analysis.

Data Analysis

The students' answers from the given 40-item test were gathered. Test results/scores were tabulated and then classified into categories with its corresponding grading scale, namely: Outstanding (90-100); Very Satisfactory (85-89); Satisfactory; Fairly Satisfactory (75-79); and Poor (below 75).

Percentage calculations were utilized to assess the academic performance in English of students in both the experimental and control groups before and after exposure to the TPACK model. Furthermore, a one-way ANOVA was employed to determine the significant differences in academic performance between the control and experimental groups before and after exposure to the TPACK model.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards by securing informed consent from all participants, ensuring their confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without any coercion. No harm came to participants, and the research received ethics committee approval. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings, analysis, and interpretation of the data. It covers the results of the students' academic performance in English in the experimental group before and after exposing to the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) model; the students' academic performance in English in the control group; the qualitative responses of teachers on the challenges of the use of the TPACK model; and the significant difference in the students' academic performance in English in the experimental and control groups before and after exposure to TPACK model.

Table 1. *Students' academic performance in English of the control group before and after exposure to traditional teaching*

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Control Group			
		Before		After	
		f	%	f	%
Outstanding	90-100	1	3.3	-	-
Very Satisfactory	85-89	-	-	2	7
Satisfactory	80-84	1	3.3	5	16
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	1	3.3	6	20
Poor	Below 75	27	90	17	57
Total		30	100	30	100

Table 1 shows that before exposure to traditional teaching, the results unveiled that there was 1 (3.3%) student categorized as Outstanding and none got a mark of Very Satisfactory. There was also 1 (3.3%) student categorized as Satisfactory, another 1 (3.3%) was Fairly Satisfactory, and 27 students (90%) were rated as poor. More than half of the class, therefore, performed poorly.

After exposure to traditional teaching, the results of the control group revealed that none of the students rated as Outstanding. However, an improvement was seen: 2 (7%) students rated Very Satisfactory, 5 (16%) students rated Satisfactory, and 6 (20%) students rated Fairly Satisfactory. Yet, 17 (57%) students were still categorized as poor. The students in this group were only given a single learning methodology which was the printed module. This group received no intervention and had their classes under modular (printed module) instruction only.

Table 2. *Students' academic performance in English of the experimental group before and after exposure to the TPACK*

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Experimental Group			
		Before		After	
		F	%	F	%
Outstanding	90-100	-	-	6	20
Very Satisfactory	85-89	-	-	-	-
Satisfactory	80-84	-	-	1	3
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	15	50	11	37
Poor	Below 75	15	50	12	40
Total		30	100	30	100

Table 2 displays that before exposure to the TPACK model, none of the students in the experimental group were rated as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, or Satisfactory. Half of the students (50%) were categorized as Fairly Satisfactory, and the other half (50%) as Poor. After TPACK exposure, 6 students (20%) were rated as Outstanding, 1 student (3%) as Satisfactory, and 11 students (37%) as Fairly Satisfactory, while 12 students (40%) remained Poor. This shows an increase in Outstanding ratings and a reduction in Poor ratings, indicating improved academic performance due to TPACK's use of technology such as PowerPoint presentations, videos, and interactive assessments.

The results align with previous studies. Joseph et al. (2022) found significant improvements in English reading and writing skills with TPACK, while Uzun (2013) and Sen and Ađır (2014) confirmed that technology-enhanced teaching methods positively impact academic achievement. Similarly, Asif et al. (2022) and Kassem (2018) demonstrated that educational technologies improve performance and participation. Overall, exposure to TPACK showed promising improvements in students' academic performance.

The study also examined challenges faced by teachers using the TPACK model, with summarized thematic responses provided.

Theme 1: Connectivity/Internet issues and unavailability of facilities.

Teachers reported frequent issues with unstable internet connections and insufficient facilities when using the TPACK model. They expressed frustration with unreliable internet, which hindered their ability to effectively deliver interactive English lessons and use video presentations. Additionally, the limited availability of school facilities, such as a single functioning projector shared among thirty teachers, forced them to use laptops or traditional board-and-chalk methods, reducing student engagement and visibility.

These challenges align with findings from Boonsue (2021), Taopan et al. (2020), and Bonifacio (n.d.), who noted that lack of technology and facilities impedes effective technology integration in teaching. Dotong et al. (2016) also highlighted that the Philippines, among other Asian countries, suffers from a shortage of computer resources, exacerbating these issues.

Theme 2: Students' limited knowledge of the technology and unavailability of device.

Teachers faced challenges with students' limited knowledge of technology and the need for personal devices. Despite assigning technology-based tasks using Microsoft Office (e.g., MS Word, MS PPT, MS Excel), many students needed help to complete these assignments due to the absence of home devices. Most students need laptops or computers and use their phones primarily for social media, with minimal exploration of educational content. Additionally, poor internet connectivity and limited computer knowledge at internet cafés further hindered their ability to use the technology effectively.

These issues are consistent with Stoilescu (2014), who found students struggled with basic applications like Excel, PowerPoint, and Word due to unfamiliarity and lack of access. Newcombe (n.d.) also noted that students' unfamiliarity with technology and lack of self-directed learning skills were significant barriers.

Theme 3: Teacher's Limited Knowledge of Technology.

A significant challenge identified was teachers' limited knowledge of technology, impacting the effective use of the TPACK model. Many teachers needed more expertise to integrate technology into their lessons, and difficulties such as setting up projectors on laptops proved time-consuming and challenging.

Supporting studies include Muhammad and Belal (2010), who found that English teachers struggled with internet use due to poor computer literacy. Sife et al. (2007) noted that many teachers need to become more familiar with the Internet and need more time to learn. Shamsul et al. (2007) suggested incorporating computer and technology education into curricula and professional development programs to address these issues.

Theme 4: Teacher's Interest/Time and Age.

Teachers reported personal challenges impacting their use of the TPACK model, including age-related declines in interest and difficulties with new technology. Some teachers found prolonged use of laptops and computers uncomfortable and struggled with new technological terms due to age. While acknowledging the benefits of technology in education, they felt it consumed too much of their time.

These observations align with Faud et al. (2020), who found that experienced teachers often need help with technology integration due to outdated skills. Absari et al. (2020) confirmed that age can reduce motivation to learn new technologies. Mueller et al. (2008) noted that lack of knowledge, skills, and confidence also hampers technology use in teaching, with older teachers often exhibiting lower self-efficacy and interest in new technologies. This study also aimed to assess the impact of TPACK on students' academic performance in English, comparing results between the control and experimental groups before and after the intervention.

Table 3. *Difference in the students' academic performance in English in the control group before exposure to traditional teaching and in the experimental group before exposure to the TPACK*

Variables	Mean \pm SD	Computed t-value	P-value	Decision pn Ho	Interpretation
Control Group Before Exposure to Traditional Teaching and Experimental Group Before Exposure to the TPACK	20.7 \pm 5.18	1.717	0.09	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 3 shows the difference in students' academic performance in English in the control group before exposure to traditional teaching and in the experimental group before exposure to the TPACK, where the computed t-value was 1.717, while the p-value was 0.09, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates no significant difference between the control group before exposure to traditional teaching and the experimental group before exposure to TPACK; hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Before exposure to the TPACK model, the experimental group had a closed or almost the same performance level as the control group. The students' scores

in the experimental group before being given an intervention were almost the same as those in the control group. This implies that the two groups performed relatively the same before the experimental groups' exposure to the TPACK.

Table 4. *Difference in the students' academic performance in English in the control group after exposure to traditional teaching and in the experimental group after exposure to the TPACK*

Variables	Mean \pm SD	Computed t-value	P-value	Decision <i>pn Ho</i>	Interpretation
Control Group After Exposure to Traditional Teaching and Experimental Group After Exposure to the TPACK	25.53 \pm 7.11 21.8 \pm 6.19	2.56	0.02	Reject <i>Ho</i>	Significant

Table 4 shows a significant difference in English academic performance between the control group, exposed to traditional teaching, and the experimental group, exposed to TPACK. The computed t-value was 2.56 with a p-value of 0.02, below the 0.05 significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

In the control group, 13 out of 30 students passed, while 18 out of 30 students passed in the experimental group. This indicates that students in the experimental group who experienced TPACK performed better.

The Dual-Coding Theory supports these findings, suggesting that integrating technology with instructional materials enhances learning by engaging auditory and visual channels. This interaction leads to more effective learning and improves academic performance. Misirli (2016) and Chang and Wu (2012) confirm that the TPACK framework positively affects student achievement. Akturk and Ozturk (2019) also support the idea that appropriately using the TPACK model can significantly boost academic performance.

Conclusions

The study reveals that the TPACK model has a notable impact on enhancing students' academic performance in English. Before exposure to traditional teaching, the control group showed a predominance of Poor ratings, which improved after traditional teaching but remained limited. In contrast, the experimental group, initially with mixed Satisfactory and Poor ratings, demonstrated a marked improvement after exposure to TPACK, with a significant increase in Outstanding and Fairly Satisfactory ratings.

The study also identifies four key challenges in using the TPACK model: Connectivity/Internet Issues and facility unavailability, Students' Limited Knowledge of Technology and Device Availability, Teachers' Limited Knowledge of Technology, and Teachers' Interest, Time, and Age. These challenges highlight barriers to the effective implementation of TPACK, impacting both teaching and learning.

Although no significant difference in academic performance was observed between the control and experimental groups before the intervention, the TPACK model significantly improved performance post-intervention. This underscores the potential of TPACK to enhance educational outcomes when effectively integrated despite the identified challenges.

Based on the conclusions, the researcher recommends the following: English teachers, or teachers in general, may utilize the TPACK model in teaching their specific learning area to supplement and enhance their teaching methodologies. Technology is a significant part of teaching and learning programs. This conveys the Department to reiterate the need for support facilities to integrate technology into the teaching-learning process. A development program is suggested for teachers' capacity building and upskilling that will improve technology integration. The experimentation of the TPACK framework/model considers broader participation to fully support the establishment of its benefits to students' academic performance in English.

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